

Data Reduction for the Split Cantilever Beam Mode III Delamination Test

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ABSTRACT

In a new Mode III delamination test recently developed by the authors, a standard split cantilever beam delamination coupon is loaded with four point loads in a complex scissoring action. Unfortunately, the specimen is relatively stiff, and data reduction is more difficult than is the case for the standard Mode I and Mode II tests. In this study, compliance calibration, beam theory, and finite element expressions for the strain energy release rate in the new test were investigated. Problems with the compliance calibration methodology arising from the very low compliance of the specimen were discovered. Conclusions about the best way to reduce the data and the reliability of the resulting G_{IIIc} are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Delaminations in laminated composites can grow in Modes I, II, and III or in some combination of these. Although tests for Mode I [1], Mode II [2] and mixed-mode delamination [3] are relatively well established, work on Mode III fracture has only recently produced a viable test method. Lee [4] developed an edge crack torsion test which involves twisting of a rectangular plate containing a starter delamination with the delamination front running parallel to the long axis of twist. This specimen is sufficiently compliant to allow for compliance calibration techniques, however specimens must be cut from laminates with a multi-axial layup, and are not similar to the standard unidirectional specimens used for Mode I (DCB) and Mode II (ENF) tests. The crack rail shear test is another method proposed for measuring G_{IIIc} [5], but this test involves a very stiff specimen, and the compliance techniques used for data reduction in the Mode I and II tests cannot be applied. A true Mode III test using a split cantilever beam (SCB) specimen and a simple data reduction scheme would have substantial advantages over these recently developed tests.

The original attempts to induce Mode III in a standard SCB specimen were made by Donaldson [6,7]. He introduced a scissoring action as illustrated in Fig. 1(a), but subsequent finite element analysis performed by Martin [8] and Sharif and Kortschot [9], indicated that the bending moment on the arms at the delamination front generates a substantial Mode II strain energy release rate (G) near the free edges. Scanning electron microscope fractographs of the delamination in specimens tested in this way [7,8] confirm that the crack propagates in Mode II at the edges of the specimen.

A solution to this problem was recently been developed by Sharif and Kortschot [9], and is illustrated in Fig. 1(b). The bending moment at the delamination front is eliminated by imposing two loads on each arm of the SCB specimen such that the net moment at the delamination front is zero. Since the two loads on each arm are different, there is still a net τ_{xy} shear stress behind the delamination front which leads to a Mode III strain energy release rate. Robinson and Song [10] have developed a similar test, although the implementation of the loading scheme is quite different in their work.

Fig. 1: Original and modified split cantilever beam Mode III delamination test.

The preferred method of data reduction for any delamination test involves a compliance calibration procedure. By experimentally measuring dC/da , G_c can be calculated without any knowledge of the material properties. In this study, the data reduction methods which are suitable for the new Mode III test are investigated in some detail. Because the loads are applied in the plane of the specimen, the compliance of the specimen is several orders of magnitude lower than the compliance of Mode I and II specimens of identical dimensions. For this reason, compliance calibration methodology may not be feasible.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS

Unidirectional, 24 ply, AS4/3501-6 (Hercules) laminates were manufactured and cured in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. The laminate was debulked after every fourth ply during the lay-up procedure. In order to simulate a 110 mm delamination, a 0.0127 mm thick polytetrafluoroethylene film was inserted between the 12th and 13th plies. The cured plate was cut using a water cooled diamond grit saw into specimens 12.5 mm deep and 150 mm long. The properties of the laminate used for finite element calculations are given in Table I.

Table I: Properties of AS4/3501-6

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
138	8.96	8.96	7.1	7.1	2.57	0.3	0.3	0.0286

G_{23} was estimated from the other moduli using a method described by Piggott [11].

TEST METHOD

One half of a simple rig for introducing the required loads is depicted in Fig. 2. It is not necessary to use loads of P and $2P$ (as in Fig. 1) in order to achieve the required moment balance. In fact, a simple free body consideration shows that the positions of loading noses a and b are not important, provided that loading pin c is collinear with the delamination front. More details about the loading rig may be found in Ref. [9]. The rig was fitted with an end plate

Finite Element Analysis

A three dimensional finite element analysis was used to plot compliance versus crack length. The C versus a curve was differentiated to determine G_c , and the result was compared with a direct virtual crack closure calculation (VCC). VCC was used to determine the distribution of strain energy release rate as a function of position along the delamination front. This procedure has been described in detail in [9] and was the basis for the acceptance of the new Mode III test.

Compliance Calibration

dC/da was determined experimentally for 19 specimens. For each specimen, the compliance was measured as a function of a as the whole specimen was advanced in the rig using a micrometer. Machine compliance was measured with an uncracked steel specimen in the rig, and was up to 20% of the specimen compliance. The experimental compliance was corrected by subtracting machine compliance at all loads. The corrected compliance was measured for 15 specimen positions in the range $39.75 \text{ mm} < a < 71.75 \text{ mm}$, where $a = 55 \text{ mm}$ represents the initial delamination length during the final test. The mean compliance at each crack length was then computed, and a best fit linear curve was calculated. The slope of this curve was used to compute dC/da .

Beam Theory

The objective of beam theory is to compute the compliance of the specimen as a function of delamination length. Because the Mode III specimen is loaded in the plane of the laminate, its shear compliance is significant fraction of the total compliance. The bending moment at the delamination front is zero at delamination initiation so that no τ_{xz} shear stresses are set up in front of the delamination and hence there is no Mode II strain energy release rate. The compliance can be split into two components, one due to bending and one due to shear, and hence the derivative of compliance can also be presented as the sum of two components:

$$dC/da = (dC/da)_{bending} + (dC/da)_{shear} \tag{2}$$

The first term $(dC/da)_{bending}$ is expected to drop to zero at $a = a_0$, the delamination initiation point, since the bending moment is zero at this point, and hence dC/da can actually be computed without consideration of the bending. Nevertheless, a full analysis follows.

Fig. 3: Specimen geometry for the beam bending computations. Note that a_0 is the distance between the loading pins, which is fixed, and da is the delamination growth.

To relate the various loads, force and moment balances are applied to a free body diagram of one arm of the SCB specimen which is treated as a cantilever beam. In the analysis which follows, an upward force and clockwise moment are considered to be positive.

Force balance:

$$W = P - Q \tag{3}$$

Moment balance:

$$-P \cdot (b + a_o) + Q \cdot a_o = 0$$

$$\therefore Q = \frac{P \cdot (b + a_o)}{a_o} \quad (4)$$

Working in region 2 closest to the root static analysis as well as the following boundary conditions reveals the following:

at $x = a+b$; $y = 0$ & $y' = 0$

$$EI \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = Q(x - b) - Px \quad (5)$$

Integrating twice and applying the b.c.'s yields:

$$EIy = -\frac{1}{6}(a + b - x)^2(2bP + Qb + Px - Qx + 2Pa - 2Qa) \quad (6)$$

Now substitute eq.'s 3 & 4 into eq.6 and set $x = b$ to get a deflection due to bending of:

$$EIy = \frac{1}{6}a^2 W(-3a_o + 2a) \quad (7)$$

In region 1 closest to the tip of the beam a similar analysis is performed. The constants of integration are determined by enforcing continuity between regions 1 and 2 when $x = b$. Start with:

$$EI \frac{d^2 y}{dy^2} = -Px \quad (8)$$

Integrating twice and enforcing continuity yields:

$$EIy = \left(-\frac{1}{6}x^3 + \frac{1}{2}xb^2 + xab + \frac{1}{2}xa^2 - \frac{1}{3}b^3 - b^2a - ba^2 - \frac{1}{3}a^3 \right) P + \left(-\frac{1}{2}xa^2 + \frac{1}{2}ba^2 + \frac{1}{3}a^3 \right) Q \quad (9)$$

Therefore the deflection due to bending at $x = 0$ in terms of the load W (from eq.'s 3 & 4) is:

$$EIy = -\frac{1}{6}W(2a_o b^2 + 6a_o ab + 3a_o a^2 - 3ba^2 - 2a^3) \quad (10)$$

Now by adding the necessary shear deflection terms to eq.'s 7 & 10 yields the total deflection at the tip ($x = 0$):

$$y_o = -\frac{W}{6EI}(2a_o b^2 + 6a_o ab + 3a_o a^2 - 3ba^2 - 2a^3) + \frac{WD^2}{8GI}(a - a_o) \quad (11)$$

and at $x = b$:

$$y_a = \frac{a^2 W}{6EI}(-3a_o + 2a) + \frac{WD^2 a}{8GI} \quad (12)$$

The displacement at the crack front can be approximated using linear interpolation.

$$\delta = \frac{a_o}{b}(y_a - y_o) + y_o \quad (13)$$

and by definition:

$$C = \frac{2\delta}{W} = \frac{2}{3bEI}(a_o^2 b^2 + 3a_o^2 ab - 3a_o ba^2 + ba^3) + \frac{D^2}{4bGI}(ba + a_o^2) \quad (14)$$

differentiate this w.r.t. a to get:

$$\frac{\partial \cdot C}{\partial \cdot a} \Big|_{a=a_o} = \frac{D^2}{4GI} \quad (15)$$

With P now representing the critical load for fracture we arrive at the strain energy release rate given by:

$$\frac{G}{P^2} = \frac{1}{2D} \cdot \frac{\partial \cdot C}{\partial \cdot a} \Big|_{a=a_o} = \frac{D}{8GI} \quad (16)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Finite Element Results

In Fig. 4, the results of virtual crack closure for a 24 ply specimen demonstrate that the modified SCB Mode III test does produce a reasonably constant Mode III strain energy release rate across the full width of the delamination. The G_{III} must decay to zero near the edges of the specimen, since τ_{yz} must drop to zero at the free surface. This means that the Mode III test is really only suitable for determining an initiation value, since the delamination will not grow in a self-similar manner. Fractographic results presented previously [9] conclusively demonstrate that the delamination does advance in Mode III in the centre of the specimen.

Fig. 4: Strain energy release rate as a function of mode and position along the delamination.

Note that although the Mode III component dominates the strain energy release rate in the new specimen, the value of dC/da is several orders of magnitude lower than is typical for Mode I or II tests. This occurs because of the low specimen compliance, and means that it will be much harder to obtain a meaningful measure of dC/da using experimental compliance calibration techniques. Even so, the dC/da is substantially larger than is typical for either the crack rail shear test [5] or for Robinson's test [10].

Fig. 5: Finite element results for compliance versus crack length together with a best fit line.

The finite element compliance data is plotted in Fig. 5. The slope of the data actually passed through a minimum at $a = 54$ mm, even though beam theory predicts the minimum should occur at $a = 55$ mm. However, the data is internally consistent, since the virtual crack closure results for total G at $a = 55$ mm matched the numerical derivative of the C vs. a data at this point. Perhaps coincidentally, the slope of the best fit straight line through all of the data in the range (as illustrated) was identical the actual slope of the data at $a = 55$ mm. It is not known whether

the local minimum was found at $a = 54$ mm because of a numerical error, or because the finite element analysis correctly deals with twisting and elastic foundation effects not included in simple beam theory. This aspect of the analysis requires further attention.

Experimental Compliance Calibration

The experimental values of mean compliance for each crack length are plotted in Fig. 6 together with standard deviations and the best fit straight line through the data. It is apparent that the compliance data are extremely noisy, although the slope of the line is virtually identical to that obtained from finite element analysis. Plots of C vs. a for individual specimens were not found to produce reliable results for dC/da , even though great care was taken during experimentation.

There are a number of potential reasons for the noise:

- 1) The specimen has very low compliance compared to that obtained in typical Mode I and Mode II tests. This occurs because the specimen arms are being deformed in plane of the laminate.
- 2) The ratio of $(dC/da)/C$ is also reduced since the compliance is dominated by the bending component, but the dC/da is entirely due to the shear component.
- 3) Waviness on the starter delamination plane causes substantial friction on this plane, which could create interlocking effects in the Mode III test.

The fibre waviness on the delamination plane is unavoidable during manufacture of a unidirectional laminate. The wave crests are aligned with the fibre direction, and mesh with troughs on the opposing surface. In a Mode III test, the delamination surfaces move perpendicular to the fibre direction, and hence the surfaces tend to interlock, and could potentially carry substantial load. This may have a pronounced effect on the measured compliance.

Fig. 6: Experimental compliance calibration results, together with beam theory and FE predictions.

Beam Theory Results

The beam theory values of compliance are plotted together with the experimental and finite element results in Fig. 6. The beam theory compliance is about 6% lower than the finite element compliance since it assumes that the arms of the specimen sit on rigid foundations and specimen twisting is not accounted for. Although the concept of a beam on elastic foundations has been built into beam theory for other fracture modes [12], this has not yet been attempted for the present geometry.

The beam theory also predicts the characteristic S-curve which would be expected as the $(dC/da)_{bending}$ drops to zero at $a = 55$ mm. This trend was observed in the finite element results, but the location of the minimum slope did not occur at $a = 55$ mm. Consequently, the beam theory predicts a value of dC/da of $2.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{N}^{-1}$, 40% lower (at $a = a_0$) than the finite element result given by VCCT.

CONCLUSIONS

The evidence suggests that it will be difficult to obtain reliable compliance calibration results using the modified SCB Mode III test. The compliance of the specimens is very low, and hence extremely accurate load and displacement measurements must be made during the calibration procedure. Part of the problem may stem from factors such as the interlocking of the pre-delaminated surfaces behind the delamination front.

Although the beam theory and finite element compliances were reasonably close, the values of dC/da varied by 40%. This is an unacceptable level of potential error, and must be resolved before the method can be put into practice. Nevertheless, the technique is convenient and makes use of specimens which are virtually identical to Mode I and Mode II SCB specimens. These factors make the technique ideal for widespread use, provided the difficulties in data reduction can be overcome.

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